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Al-Farabi Kazakh National University – the forge of Kazakh elite

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Abstract. There is much to say about the Kazakh National University. Its long-way traditions, history, culture, student life and the inspiring stuff. The authors do emphasis on each aspect briefly. There is general description of infrastructure of the University.

Key words: education, Kazakhstan, University, students, pedagogy

The flagship of higher education in Kazakhstan, the leading University named after Al-Farabi was founded in 1934, an order was issued to faculty members and 54 students enrolling the first two faculties - Mathematics and Physics and Biology. Now in the university there are 14 faculties, including legal and international relations. The university trains about 20,000 students from all regions of the country, as well as near and far abroad, employs 2,000 faculty members, including more than a thousand lecturers and PhDs, professors and associate professors, more than 60 academicians, winners of more than seventy public and registered premiums. The university trains specialists in 180 bachelor's, master's and doctoral programs.

The University has made a great contribution to the development of economy, culture, science and education of Kazakhstan, has become the largest source of manpower in the entire Central Asian region. High quality education, international recognition, active research activities, innovation, the strongest faculty and gifted graduates that's what Kazakh National University today can be proud of the.

Innovations introduced in recent years in the management system, the educational process and scientific research have made it possible for breakthrough in the world rankings. In 2013, the University was first among the universities of Central Asia and Kazakhstan entered the top 300 best universities in the world of international rating QS

World University Rankings, ranking 299 among 300 most successful internationally recognized universities. This group consisted of only three universities of the CIS countries - Moscow State University, St. Petersburg State University and Al-Farabi Kazakh National University.

Teacher this is not the one who has knowledge, and he who leads them. He points the way to the heights of thought, moral heights, spiritual and physical perfection. "The mediocre teacher sets. A good teacher explains. Outstanding teacher shows. The great teacher inspires" – so said thinker W. Ward, and there are a great bunch of inspiring teachers the University. Due to the fact that KazNU is one of the oldest institution of higher learning classical republic, organized by the Decree of the Office of the Provincial Committee of the Kazakh WKB (b) on 13 November 1933. Over the 76 years of its existence the University has made a great contribution to the development of the economy, political and legal life, culture, science and education multinational Kazakhstan and became a stronghold of the entire system of higher schools in the country. He formed and to this day remains the largest source of manpower higher professional qualification, one of the main centers of research work in the Republic.

KazNU has a great educational, scientific, innovative and productive potential, which is used to prepare highly qualified specialists, further integration into international educational space, development of basic and applied researches and their implementation in practice. Results of scientific research are successfully implemented, for instance, by using in the production or manufacture. Many scientific groups have contracts with large domestic and international enterprises and according to the agreements they work on developing technology and production.

Today, Al-Farabi University is the first classical university of our country and the first winner of the Prize of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan "For achievements in quality" among all Kazakhstani higher education institutions. It is, without doubt, permanent leader in the General ranking Kazakh universities. In 2009, it entered the list of 600 best universities in the world of 16,000 according to the prestigious ranking of universities "Times". The university has trained more than 20,000 students from all regions of our country, as well as near and far abroad.

The faculty of the University has more than 2,500 people, including 400 doctors, professors and 800 associate professors, 200 domestic and foreign doctors of philosophy (Ph.D.) Al-Farabi University provides a wide range of professions from more than 180 humanitarian, scientific, technical specialties of undergraduate, graduate, doctorate.

The mission of the University is to train competitive specialists with modern elite

of higher education, focused on solving the problems of intensive development of the most important areas of economy, science and social life of the country. Today, the Al-Farabi University has developed not only as a Republican, but also as an international center of education in the Central Asian region with worthy positioning in the global educational space.

The university is successfully operating in Kazakhstan with its unique scientific infrastructure, which consists of 24 research institutes, research centers and the Science and Technology Park. In the University scientific ideas are developed and practically implemented, 25 are active dissertation councils. According to current estimates, including foreign ones, the share of the al-Farabi is more than 50% of research works carried out in the universities of the country. There is also a unique information intranet system "Univer" which combines network of more than 3500 modern computers.

"Univer" is a local information network of the University, which provides a high level of automation of the educational process. It awakens the initiative of students and their direct interest in the outcome of learning. In addition, this technology delivers daily and well-protected control over the actions of each teacher and a student. Accessibility and transparency of Intranet system creates a whole new level of protection against corruption.

To date it has a modern office equipment. In large auditoriums University classes are held using interactive whiteboards. The number of computer allows each class students, graduate students to master modern information technologies. Today, all departments, each structural unit of the university dormitory are connected to the World Wide Web. From this academic year, the school buildings, university dormitories and the rest of the student campus operates a wireless network access to the Internet WI-FI. Last year it was discovered the largest in the city and has no analogues among universities CIS Internet cafe with 300 seats. The campus operates a facility for high-grade education and leisure: beautiful sports center with a gym, sports fields and sections, medical center, private cinema, a network of reading rooms, a powerful library that provides students the necessary educational literature.

KazNU is one of the best universities in Kazakhstan with excellent infrastructure and a large number of highly qualified professors and teachers who effectively train and teach a lot of students working, studying and living in dynamic and exciting atmosphere.

Nonresident full-time students live in the hostel. There are 13 hostels, all of which differ in comfort, safety and all the conditions for living. The University has its own

cinema, located in KazGUGrad where weekly shows are performed world premieres of new films for the students and faculty of the University. Moreover, on picturesque shores of Lake Issyk-Kul there is a sports complex with landscaped University boarding house in which students and teachers take a rest from studying each year.

Summing up, Kazakh National University named after al-Farabi has long standing traditions and boasts many years of experience in scientific research, which is famous in the post-Soviet space. Nowadays, it is a leading institution in the system of higher education of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which is the first one to pass international accreditation on all specialties and levels.

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